

Socio-cognitive determinants of lifestyle behavior in the context of dementia risk reduction: a population-based study in the Netherlands

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1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Unhealthy lifestyle behavior increases the risk of dementia. Various socio-cognitive
3 determinants of behavior influence whether individuals persist in or alter unhealthy behaviors.

4 **Objective:** This study identifies relevant determinants of behavior associated to dementia risk.

5 **Methods:** 4,104 Dutch individuals (40 to 79 years) completed a screening questionnaire exploring
6 lifestyle behaviors associated with dementia risk. Subsequently, 3,065 respondents who actively
7 engaged in one or more unhealthy behaviors completed a follow-up questionnaire investigating
8 determinants of these behaviors. Cross-tables were used to assess the accuracy of participants'
9 perceptions regarding their behavior compared to Dutch lifestyle recommendations. Confidence
10 Interval-Based Estimation of Relevance (CIBER) was used to identify the most relevant determinants
11 of behavior based on visual inspection and interpretation.

12 **Results:** Among the respondents, 91.3% reported at least one, while 65% reported two or more
13 unhealthy lifestyle behaviors associated to dementia risk. Many of them were not aware they did not
14 adhere to Dutch lifestyle recommendations. The most relevant determinants identified include attitudes
15 (i.e., lacking a passion for cooking and finding pleasure in drinking alcohol or smoking), inaccurate
16 social comparison perceptions (i.e., overestimating healthy diet intake and underestimating alcohol
17 intake), and particularly low perceived behavioral control (i.e., regarding changing physical inactivity,
18 altering diet behavior, and smoking cessation).

19 **Conclusion:** There is promising potential for reducing dementia risk through lifestyle changes in the
20 Netherlands. Dementia risk reduction interventions are likely to be the most successful if they focus on
21 enhancing accurate perceptions about engagement in unhealthy behaviors, while strengthening
22 perceived control to change these behaviors.

23

24 *Keywords: Prevention, Dementia, Public Health, Health Promotion, Health Risk Behaviors, Behavioral*
25 *Medicine, Alzheimer's Disease*

26

27 **1. Background**

28 A growing body of evidence has identified modifiable risk and protective factors for dementia [1, 2].
29 These insights pave the way for the development of preventive interventions to reduce the rising
30 incidence of dementia. A crucial aspect of many of these interventions revolves around multidomain
31 approaches encouraging healthy lifestyle changes [3], particularly in middle aged and older individuals.
32 Across lifespan, a wide variety of modifiable lifestyle factors have been associated with dementia risk
33 [1], such as physical inactivity, unhealthy diet, high alcohol intake, psychological stress, smoking, low
34 sleep quality, and limited social and cognitive stimulating activities [4-6]. All these lifestyle factors are
35 influenced by a set of behavior specific socio-cognitive determinants that determine whether individuals
36 persist in or alter unhealthy behavior [7, 8]. Examples of socio-cognitive determinants are attitudes (i.e.,
37 a latent disposition or tendency to respond with favorableness or unfavorableness to a behavior), social
38 norms (i.e., the perceived social pressure to perform or not perform a behavior), and perceived
39 behavioral control (i.e., the perceived degree of being capable of, or have control over, performing a
40 behavior) [9].

41 While extensive literature exists regarding specific lifestyle-related determinants of behavior [8], there
42 is limited insight into these determinants in the context of dementia risk reduction. For example, the
43 Motivation to Change Lifestyle and Health Behaviors for Dementia Risk Reduction Scale (MCLHB-
44 DRR) offers understanding in determinants of generic lifestyle change [10], without delving into
45 determinants of specific behaviors, such as attitudes about alcohol or self-efficacy towards smoking
46 cessation [10]. This is a limitation because individuals often express more positivity towards broad
47 lifestyle changes while they are more reluctant towards altering particular unhealthy behaviors [11].
48 Furthermore, it is well-known that determinants are highly behavior specific, which makes it impossible
49 to intuitively select the most relevant determinants, even for experts in behavior change [12]. Therefore,
50 our aim is to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of socio-cognitive determinants of specific
51 lifestyle behaviors in the context of dementia risk reduction. These insights allow selecting appropriate
52 behavior change methods that aim to establish change in these determinants via interventions [7, 8]. To
53 this end, the present study is embedded within a larger project including a clinical trial on a digitally

54 supported lifestyle program to promote brain health among older adults (LETHE, clinicaltrials.gov
55 identifier NCT05565170) [13]. LETHE is a multinational feasibility study testing a multidomain
56 intervention for risk reduction of cognitive decline and dementia in older adults, delivered through a
57 hybrid model, including in-person as well as digitally supported activities. The findings of the present
58 study inform the development of practical applications that aim to promote behavior change and are
59 embedded in the LETHE intervention [14]. The recently published report by Alzheimer's Disease
60 International emphasizes the critical need to explore novel, comprehensive approaches in reducing
61 dementia risk [15].

62 **Methods**

63 In the Netherlands, a screening questionnaire was administered to identify individuals who engaged in
64 unhealthy lifestyle behaviors, who were then invited for a follow-up questionnaire exploring
65 determinants of these behaviors. The study protocol was pre-registered [16] and relevant supportive
66 materials and datasets to replicate the findings are open access available [17]. The findings are reported
67 by employing the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE)
68 checklist [18].

69 ***2.1 Recruitment***

70 In September 2022, respondents were recruited via the ISO-certified Internet research agency
71 Flycatcher that has a large panel in the Netherlands. Dutch speaking respondents aged 40 to 79 years
72 were eligible for participation because associations between lifestyle and dementia have been well-
73 established in mid-life and late-life [19, 20].

74 A sample size estimation indicated that a minimum of 4,000 respondents were required for the screening
75 questionnaire to ensure sufficient statistical power for analyses using variables from the follow-up
76 questionnaire. This estimation accounted for population prevalence per lifestyle behavior (i.e., smoking
77 had the lowest population prevalence, $\approx 20\%$ [21]), response rate expectancy of Flycatcher ($\approx 75\%$), and
78 accuracy of parameter estimates (i.e., ability to detect correlations coefficients of 0.2 with half-width of
79 .1 and confidence interval of 95% [22]).

80 ***2.2 Development of the questionnaires***

81 The questionnaires were developed through an iterative process, involving literature research, a prior
82 interview study ($n=23$) [11], and think-aloud sessions with experts in dementia risk reduction ($n=4$).
83 Questionnaires were pre-tested with middle-aged and older individuals ($n=3$) with a low socio-
84 economic position who are part of a Dutch advisory board that consults about research. The iterative
85 and collaborative development process helped to refine our approach to select respondents based on a
86 screening questionnaire that operationalized the Lifestyle for BRAin health (LIBRA) index. LIBRA is
87 a validated index for assessing dementia risk and is based on 12 modifiable risk and protective factors
88 [6, 23]. For example, the experts provided guidance about the questionnaires and inclusion cut-offs
89 based on their experience with research on dementia risk.

90 The follow-up questionnaire included items to assess socio-cognitive determinants of specific lifestyle
91 behaviors. These determinants were derived from multiple theories to achieve a comprehensive
92 understanding of their impact [8, 24]. The items were constructed using available definitions of
93 behavioral determinants alongside with corresponding measurement instructions [25]. Drawing on
94 insights from literature and the prior interview study [11], specific items were developed to assess
95 determinants that are potentially relevant to specific lifestyle behaviors in context of dementia risk. To
96 exemplify, interviewees with unhealthy diet patterns frequently mentioned they did not enjoy cooking,
97 which resulted in the development of specific items to assess attitudes towards cooking. The think-
98 aloud sessions with experts and a pre-test with middle-aged and older individuals helped to refine these
99 items in terms of their face and content validity.

100 ***2.2.1 The screening questionnaire***

101 The aim of the screening questionnaire was to identify respondents who actively engaged in one or
102 more unhealthy lifestyle behaviors associated with dementia risk. Therefore, the screening
103 questionnaire employed the 9-item Rapid Assessment of Physical Activity (RAPA) [26], to identify
104 respondents who did not adhere to Dutch recommendations of doing at least 150 minutes of moderate-
105 to-vigorous activity per week spread over several days [27]. The 14-item Mediterranean Diet Adherence
106 Screener (MEDAS14; range from 0-14) [28] allowed to select respondents with low adherence to the
107 Mediterranean Diet (i.e., score ≤ 5). In Dutch diet guidelines the Mediterranean Diet is exemplified as

108 it aligns with most recommendations (i.e., high consumption of vegetables, fruits, whole-grain products,
109 nuts, legumes, oils, unsaturated fat, poultry, and fish whereas it is characterized by lower intake of red
110 or processed meat, high-fat dairy, hard fats, salt, and sugar-sweetened beverages [29]). The Alcohol Use
111 Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT) [30, 31] was used to identify respondents who consumed over 1
112 unit of alcohol per day on average, aligning with Dutch recommendations [29]. Self-constructed items
113 were employed to identify respondents who smoked and to assess the number of cigarettes (or other
114 tobacco products) they consumed per day [32]. Engagement in social and cognitive activities was
115 assessed using a self-constructed activity list with 12 items, based on earlier operationalization in
116 dementia prevention research [33]. Respondents were classified as socially and cognitively inactive
117 based on a <median-split of weekly activities in our sample [32]. Other health-related modifiable risk
118 that are included in LIBRA were assessed by asking respondents if a doctor had ever informed them
119 about having coronary heart disease, renal dysfunction, diabetes, high cholesterol, hypertension, and
120 depression [34]. Obesity (Body Mass Index, BMI ≥ 30) was calculated based on self-reported length
121 and weight (i.e., BMI = kg/m²).

122 ***2.2.2 The follow-up questionnaire***

123 Respondents who reported at least one unhealthy lifestyle behavior on the screening questionnaire were
124 invited to participate in the follow-up questionnaire exploring determinants of these behaviors. The
125 follow-up questionnaire employed a set of self-constructed items assessing determinants separately for
126 physical activity, adherence to the Mediterranean diet, alcohol intake, smoking, and engagement in
127 social and cognitive activities. All respondents completed items on physical activity, diet, and social
128 and cognitive activities because, to an extent, everyone engages in these behaviors. The items on alcohol
129 and smoking were only completed by participants who reported to drink alcohol or smoke.

130 The follow-up questionnaire utilized tailored sets of items for each specific lifestyle behavior to
131 operationalize potentially relevant determinants concerning these behaviors. The final version of the
132 follow-up questionnaire assessed the following subdomains for each lifestyle behavior separately: (a)
133 beliefs about engaging in sufficient levels of a particular behavior, (b) intentions to change behavior,
134 (c) attitudes, (d) risk perceptions, (e) social and environmental influences, and (f) behavioral control.

135 **2.5 Data analyses**

136 Distribution and spread were calculated for sample characteristics in SPSS. A summative LIBRA-score
137 was calculated ranging from -5.9 to +12.7, with higher scores indicating a higher relative risk for
138 cognitive decline and dementia [6]. Cross-tables were calculated to assess the extent to which
139 respondents believed to engage in sufficient levels of a particular behavior, compared to Dutch lifestyle
140 recommendations used as cut-offs for inviting respondents for the follow-up questionnaire.

141 Successively, per lifestyle behavior the most relevant determinants were identified by using Confidence
142 Interval-Based Estimation of Relevance (CIBER) [12, 35]. CIBER was favored over regression
143 analyses due to potential distortion caused by theoretical overlap among determinants [36]. Utilizing
144 diamond plots, CIBER visualizes univariate distributions of items that measure behavior determinants
145 and their bivariate estimated association with behavior [12]. This visualization method is specifically
146 developed to assess relevance of determinants based on inspection and interpretation. The CIBER plots
147 visualizing scoring distribution and means, provide an indication of room for improvement at the
148 determinant level [35]. In an intervention context, altering a behavioral determinant is relevant only
149 when there is room for improvement. For instance, enhancing knowledge is meaningful if respondents
150 currently lack knowledge. Additionally, CIBER plots the zero-order associations between determinants
151 and the outcome behavior. In terms of an intervention it is relevant to alter a determinant if this correlates
152 with healthier behavior [35]. To exemplify, increasing knowledge is only relevant if it is associated with
153 healthier behavior.

154 The *CIBER* function is part of the R package *behaviorchange* [37]. The *binaryCIBER* function was used
155 to identify the most relevant determinants for physical inactivity since the outcome of RAPA is binary
156 (i.e., sedentary and underactive versus physically active). Determinants of the other lifestyle behaviors
157 were assessed with continuous outcome variables. Specifically, summative outcome scores were
158 composed for the following four behaviors separately: Mediterranean diet, weekly units of alcohol
159 intake, daily number of cigarettes (including other tobacco products), and weekly social and cognitive
160 activities.

161

162 **2.6 Ethics**

163 The study protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Health, Medicine
 164 and Life Sciences of Maastricht University, the Netherlands (FHML-REC/2022/064). Participants
 165 provided digital informed consent and received a reward through Flycatcher of approximately €0.60
 166 (≈\$0.65) for the screening questionnaire and €2.00 (≈\$2.18) for the follow-up questionnaire.

167 **2. Results**

168 The screening questionnaire was completed by 4,104 individuals aged 40 to 79 years (Table 1). Of the
 169 respondents, 91.3% ($n = 3,746/4,104$) reported at least one unhealthy lifestyle behavior, while 65%
 170 ($n = 2,666/4,104$) reported two or more. A total of 3,746 respondents were invited for the follow-up
 171 questionnaire, which was completed by 81.6% ($n = 3,056/3,746$).

Table 1. *Sample characteristics and risk factors (N=4,104)*

<u>Age in years</u> , Mean (SD); min to max	59.1 (10.57); 40 to 79
<u>Gender</u> , male (%) /female (%)	1710 (41.7) / 2394 (58.3)
<u>Migration background</u> , N (%)	
First generation	158 (3.8)
Second generation	347 (8.5)
<u>Highest completed educational level</u> , N (%)	
Low	823 (20.1)
Medium	1545 (37.6)
High	1736 (42.3)
<u>LIBRA-factors</u> , N (%)	
Physical inactivity*	2172 (52.9%)
Low adherence to Mediterranean diet*	2237 (54.5%)
Overconsumption of alcohol*	1005 (24.5%)
Smoking*	456 (11.1%)
Low social and cognitive activity*	2057 (50.1%)
Coronary heart disease	652 (15.9%)
Renal dysfunction	84 (2.0%)
Diabetes	434 (10.6%)
High blood cholesterol	1257 (30.6%)
Obesity**	918 (22.4%)
Hypertension	1400 (34.1%)
Depression	734 (17.9%)
<u>LIBRA-score</u> , Mean (SD); min to max	0.35 (2.90); -5.9 to +10.6
Percentiles, 25;50;75	-2.6; -0.5; 1.6

*Protective factors are inverted and represented as risk factors to enhance interpretability. * Behaviors used to invite respondents for the follow-up questionnaire. ** Calculated with data of 4,099 respondents.*

172 **3.1 Perceptions about behavior versus lifestyle recommendations**

173 Cross-tables (Table 2) demonstrate that 39.4% of the respondents perceived to engage in sufficient
 174 levels of physical activity while they did not meet lifestyle recommendations. Additionally, 54.8% of
 175 the respondents considered their diet as healthy while they had low adherence to the Mediterranean diet.
 176 Among the respondents consuming over 1 unit of alcohol per day on average, 43.2% was unaware that
 177 their drinking behavior exceeded the recommended level. Additionally, 51.5% of respondents perceived
 178 to be socially and cognitively active, despite being in the lowest quartile of a score indicating the
 179 frequency of weekly activities.

Table 2. *Perceptions about behavior versus lifestyle recommendations*

Do you think you do enough weekly physical activity? (n = 3,065)		
	<u>Physically inactive, N (%)</u>	<u>Physically active, N (%)</u>
Yes	701 (39.4%)	985 (76.5%)
Somewhat	680 (38.2%)	256 (19.9%)
No	287 (22.3%)	46 (3.6%)
Do you think you eat healthy? (n = 3,065)		
	<u>Low Mediterranean diet, N (%)</u>	<u>Medium-high Mediterranean diet, N (%)</u>
Yes	1007 (54.8%)	943 (76.8%)
Somewhat	753 (41.0%)	273 (22.2%)
No	77 (4.2%)	12 (1.0%)
Do you think you overconsume alcohol? (n = 2,410)		
	<u>Overconsumption of alcohol, N (%)</u>	<u>Regular consumption of alcohol, N (%)</u>
Yes	93 (11.1%)	4 (.2%)
Somewhat	384 (45.7%)	122 (5.5%)
No	363 (43.2%)	1444 (64.9%)
Do you think that you are socially and actively engaged in life? (n = 3,065)		
	<u>Low activities, N (%)</u>	<u>Medium-high activities, N (%)</u>
Yes	423 (51.5%)	1506 (67.1%)
Somewhat	321 (39.1%)	601 (26.8%)
No	77 (9.4%)	137 (6.1%)

Note. Physically inactive is doing less than 150 min of moderate or 60 min of vigorous activity spread over several days of the week. Low adherence to Mediterranean diet is a summative score ≤ 5 on the MEDAS14. Overconsumption of alcohol is drinking over 1 unit per day on average. Low activity is based on the lowest 25% of weekly social and cognitive activities.

180

181

182 **3.2 Interpretating CIBER-plots to indicate relevant behavioral determinants**

183 Figure 1 and Figure 2 present the CIBER-plots, which visualize scoring distributions using scatterplots
184 and means, along with associations between determinants and actual behavior. Supporting data is
185 provided in the Supplementary Files.

186 **3.2.1 Intentions to change lifestyle behavior**

187 The visualized scoring distributions reveal that respondents have moderate intentions to change specific
188 lifestyle behaviors, with scores concentrating around 3 on a 5-point scale (Fig 1 and 2). Intentions
189 towards mitigating the future risk for dementia are slightly higher compared to more generalized
190 intentions towards behavior change. Although these distributions are implying room for improvement,
191 the associations between intentions and actual healthy lifestyle behavior are weak, indicating limited
192 relevance.

193 **3.2.2 Attitudes**

194 Distributions and associations show the relevance of being passionate about cooking and finding
195 pleasure in drinking alcohol or smoking (Fig 1 and 2). Specifically, mean scores for passion about
196 cooking are below 3 on a 5-point scale, whereas being more passionate is moderately associated to a
197 healthier diet. Additionally, scoring distributions reveal that respondents experience pleasure when
198 drinking alcohol or smoking, with means falling above 3.5 on a 5-point scale. This suggests an
199 opportunity to reduce these positive attitudes, especially considering that pleasure is moderately to
200 strongly associated with increased consumption levels.

201 **3.2.3 Risk perceptions**

202 Distributions reveal that respondents have rather realistic risk perceptions about the negative impact of
203 unhealthy lifestyle behaviors on physical health, brain health, and dementia risk (Fig 1 and 2).
204 Specifically, scores are concentrating between 3 and 4 on a 5-point scale, indicating limited room for
205 enhancement of these risk perceptions, which is further indicated by limited associations with actual
206 lifestyle behavior.

207

208 **3.2.4 Social influences**

209 Scoring distributions show that respondents perceive limited influence from others on their lifestyle
210 behavior, with means falling below 2.5 on a 5-point scale (Fig 1 and 2). While this is suggesting room
211 for improvement, the weak associations are indicating that more accurate perceptions about social
212 influences have limited influence on actual health behavior.

213 Compared to others, respondents perceived their diet as healthy, with scores concentrating between 3
214 and 4 on a 5-point scale (Fig 1 and 2). This suggests room to improve more accurate comparative
215 perceptions, especially considering that 54.5% had a low adherence to the Mediterranean diet (i.e., a
216 score ≤ 5). Similarly, the scoring distributions are indicating there is room to enhance more accurate
217 perceptions about alcohol intake compared to others. Scores are concentrating between 1 and 3 on a 5-
218 point scale, while 24.5% of the respondents that drink exceed the recommended level of one unit of
219 alcohol per day.

220 **3.2.5 Behavioral control**

221 Perceived control over behavior emerged as one of the most relevant determinants across various
222 lifestyle behaviors (Fig 1 and 2). Specifically, mean scores among sedentary and underactive
223 respondents are below 3 on a 5-point scale, suggesting room for improvement. Strong associations are
224 indicating that higher perceived control correlates with increased physical activity. Additionally, mean
225 scores for perceived control over changing diet patterns are concentrating around 3.5 on a 5-point scale,
226 indicating limited potential for improvement. Nevertheless, higher control moderately associates with
227 having a healthier diet. Regarding smoking cessation scores are concentrating around 2 on a 5-point
228 scale, indicating room for improvement and low perceived control strongly correlates with more
229 smoking behavior. In contrast, respondents reported high perceived control over decreasing their
230 alcohol intake, with scores concentrating above 4 on a 5-point scale, suggesting limited room for
231 improvement.

232 **3.3 Explained variance**

233 The determinants included in the CIBER-plots demonstrated varying levels of explanatory power
234 (95%CI of R^2). Specifically, determinants included for alcohol intake had the highest explanatory

235 power, explaining 38-45% of the variance, followed by smoking (19-34%), physical activity (20-26%),
236 and diet (18-23%). In contrast, the determinants included for social and cognitive activity only
237 explained a very limited amount of the variance in those activities, ranging from 3% to 5%.
238 Furthermore, none of the determinants included for social and cognitive activity were identified as
239 relevant based on the distributions of scores and associations.

240 **4. Discussion**

241 ***4.1 Key findings***

242 Our findings reveal that a significant proportion of the Dutch public has room for improvement in at
243 least one (91.3%) or even multiple (65%) lifestyle behaviors. Many of our respondents were not aware
244 of this and perceived to engage in sufficient levels of healthy behavior, while they did not adhere to
245 Dutch lifestyle recommendations. The most relevant determinants that were identified include attitudes
246 (i.e., lacking a passion for cooking and finding pleasure in drinking alcohol or smoking), inaccurate
247 social comparison perceptions (i.e., overestimating healthy diet intake and underestimating alcohol
248 intake), and particularly low perceived behavioral control (i.e., regarding physical inactivity, changing
249 diet behavior, and smoking cessation).

250 ***4.2 Interpretation***

251 In the present study, we observed slightly lower prevalence figures for unhealthy lifestyle behaviors
252 compared to Dutch figures reported in 2022. Specifically, we found 52.9% versus 56% for physical
253 inactivity, 54.5% versus 71% for an unhealthy diet, 24.5% versus 56% for drinking over one unit of
254 alcohol a day, and 11.1% versus 19% for smoking [38]. This suggests that our findings are – if anything
255 – an underrepresentation of the potential for dementia risk reduction through lifestyle improvements in
256 the Netherlands. Based on our figures, we observed that 91.3% of our respondents could improve at
257 least one, and 65% two or more lifestyle behaviors that would reduce the future risk of dementia,
258 highlighting the high potential for dementia risk reduction in the Netherlands. Moreover, according to
259 the Netherlands Institute for Social Research, the prevalence of unhealthy lifestyle behaviors in the
260 Netherlands is relatively moderate compared to various other European countries, except for alcohol

261 intake, which is high in the Netherlands [39]. This highlights the considerable population-level potential
262 for reducing dementia risk through lifestyle-related changes within a European context.

263 Many of our respondents held misconceptions regarding their current engagement in healthy lifestyle
264 behavior compared to Dutch recommendations. These misconceptions can be attributed to insufficient
265 awareness concerning guidelines as well as to an overestimation of healthy behavior and an
266 underestimation of unhealthy ones. It is well-documented that having misconceptions can undermine
267 the willingness to initiate change in unhealthy behaviors [40, 41], which may explain why intentions
268 towards changing specific behaviors were limited within our sample. In a previous qualitative study,
269 we found that interviewees were relatively positive towards a healthier lifestyle but ambivalent about
270 changing specific unhealthy behaviors. For instance, they mitigated the negative effects of unhealthy
271 behavior, suggested to compensate for it, and felt that an immediate health threat was needed to initiate
272 lifestyle change [11]. The limited motivation towards changing specific lifestyle behaviors also aligns
273 with prior quantitative research that shows that only 32% of physically inactive individuals, 18% of
274 those not adhering to diet recommendations, and 29% of those consuming high levels of alcohol
275 expressed positive intentions to change these behaviors [42]. The Protection Motivation Theory offers
276 a useful framework for understanding how misconceptions about engagement in health behavior can
277 mitigate intentions to change unhealthy behavior, considering threat appraisal (i.e., perceived severity
278 and susceptibility) and coping appraisal (i.e., response efficacy and self-efficacy) [43]. Specifically,
279 individuals with misconceptions about their personal engagement in unhealthy behavior may have
280 lower perceptions of susceptibility, making them less inclined to act [41]. This offers an explanation as
281 to why respondents with reasonably accurate risk perceptions regarding the negative effects of
282 unhealthy behavior did not necessarily engage in healthier behavior.

283 Aligned with the Protection Motivation Theory, our findings also highlight the importance of perceived
284 behavioral control, a concept akin to self-efficacy [43, 44]. It is well-described that individuals with
285 higher perceived control over their behavior, often attributed to overcoming specific barriers to
286 performing the behavior [44], are more inclined to make positive lifestyle changes [45]. Many
287 participants in our sample believed they had limited control over changing unhealthy behaviors, which

288 may further contribute to their limited willingness to change. It is worth noting that many of our
289 respondents who drank alcohol expressed a high sense of control over their intake levels and
290 underestimated their consumption behavior compared to that of others. It is known that people who
291 drink alcohol are often overconfident about their ability to control their intake [46], while
292 simultaneously they are overestimating others' and underestimating their own alcohol consumption
293 levels [47].

294 The findings emphasize that motivating individuals to reduce dementia risk through lifestyle changes
295 should prioritize enhancing accurate perceptions of own behavior and strengthening behavioral control.
296 Self-monitoring methods like measuring step count or completing a food diary can decrease
297 misconceptions about the adherence to recommendations and may be a stepping stone towards positive
298 lifestyle changes through the mere measurement effect [48, 49]. Providing timely, individualized, non-
299 punitive, and actionable feedback may further encourage healthy lifestyle improvements by making
300 individuals aware of their own behavior and by providing specific cues to action [50, 51]. Goal setting
301 and action planning methods are also well-known methods to subsequently enhance perceived
302 behavioral control, preferably by gradually increasing the achievability of certain behavioral changes
303 [30]. Formulating coping responses to overcome specific barriers and cope with difficult situations may
304 further facilitate goal achievement [52]. In our qualitative research [11], we observed that low perceived
305 control frequently resulted from earlier failed attempts to change lifestyle behavior for dementia risk
306 reduction. This underscores the importance of providing support to individuals experiencing a relapse,
307 for example by encouraging them to view it as a part of the lifestyle change process they go through,
308 and use it as an opportunity to learn from the experience [53].

309 ***4.3 Practical applications***

310 The research findings are currently used to shape the development of behavior change interventions
311 that will be integrated in the digital LETHE intervention to prevent cognitive decline and dementia [13].
312 LETHE utilizes a smartphone app and Fitbit smartwatch to monitor lifestyle behavior. One of the
313 features under development is a system to classify participants into weekly adherence pathways (i.e.,
314 green, yellow, red). This system would enable lifestyle monitoring to offer personalized feedback and

315 support. Furthermore, smartphone functionalities are under development to empower participants to
316 actively monitor a range of lifestyle behaviors. For instance, via a weekly performance assessment with
317 motivational feedback messages. This example on LETHE illustrates how the research findings can
318 guide the development of practical applications supporting behavior change by enabling more accurate
319 perceptions of engagement in lifestyle behavior and by strengthening control over initiating healthy
320 changes. Additionally, the findings generate relevant directions for interventions and endeavors that are
321 part of the Prevention Agreement [54] and National Dementia Strategy [55] recently launched by the
322 government of the Netherlands.

323 ***4.4 Strengths and limitations***

324 This cross-sectional study implemented several measures to enhance the credibility of findings. The
325 study protocol was pre-registered [16] ensuring transparency and minimizing the risk of reporting bias.
326 Additionally, all supportive materials and data are open access available to promote reproducibility and
327 encourage future research endeavors.

328 A strength of the current study is that the recruitment occurred via a specialized research agency
329 allowing efficient data collection in a large sample of the Dutch population. However, this also
330 introduced risks for selection bias because individuals without Internet access are not able to take part
331 in the panel. According to Statistics Netherlands, in 2023 nearly 80% of the Dutch population has at
332 least basic digital skills, which ranks the Netherlands at the European top [56]. In the study, we also
333 incorporated a robust screening process for selecting respondents based on the validated LIBRA-index.
334 In this respect, a limitation is that unvalidated items were used to operationalize the assessment of social
335 and cognitive activity, leading to potential measurement inaccuracies which have limited the
336 exploratory power in this aspect. New and more comprehensive follow-up research is needed – and
337 underway – to explore relevant determinants of social and cognitive behavior thoroughly. Additionally,
338 new research is underway to investigate how differences in demographics, especially socio-economic
339 status, impact socio-cognitive determinants of lifestyle behavior, seeking to better understand disparities
340 in dementia risk.

341

342 **4.5 Conclusions**

343 Our study reveals a promising potential for reducing dementia risk through lifestyle behavior change in
344 the Netherlands. To effectively promote lifestyle behavior change for dementia risk reduction the
345 findings indicate that interventions should focus on enhancing accurate perceptions of personal
346 engagement in unhealthy behavior compared to lifestyle recommendations, while strengthening
347 behavioral control over adopting a healthier lifestyle.

348

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355 **Conflict of interest**

356 The authors have no conflict of interest to report.

357 **Data availability**

358 The materials and datasets supporting the conclusions of this article are available on the Open Science
359 Framework through <https://osf.io/eqbgr/>.

360

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Figure 1

Means and associations (d) with adherence to physical activity ($R^2 = [.20, .26]$), $n = 3,065$

Figure 2

Means and associations (r) with alcohol intake (R² = [.38, .45]), n = 2,410

Means and associations (r) with number of cigarettes (R² = [.19, .34]), n = 356

Means and associations (r) with social and cognitive activity (R² = [.03, .05]), n = 3,065

Figure 1